

Synthesis and characterization of a few bis- and tris-complexes of iron(II) with 3,5-dimethyl-1-(4',6'-dimethyl-2'-pyrimidyl)pyrazole [DP_{ym}P_z]

Durgadas Mukherjee

Department of Chemistry, Mahadevananda Mahavidyalaya, Monirampore, Barrackpore, 24-Parganas (N), West Bengal, India

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Abstract : Solid iron(II) complexes [Fe(DP_{ym}P_z)₂X₂].nH₂O (X = Cl, Br, SCN, n = 0, 2) and [Fe(DP_{ym}P_z)₃]X₂.nH₂O (X = ClO₄, BF₄ and I, n = 0, 2) have been isolated and characterized. The μ_{eff} values for bis complexes lie in the range 5.1–5.6 B.M. while this range for the tris complexes is 2.32–2.49 B.M. at 298 K. The diffuse reflectance spectra of all the iron complexes indicate an ${}^5T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g$ transition. IR data point out the pyrazolyl nitrogen (tertiary) and one of the pyrimidyl nitrogens of DP_{ym}P_z as bonding sites in forming these complexes and counter ions (X) are coordinated in the bis-species while the same retain their ionic character in the tris complexes. The solid state EPR spectrum of [Fe(DP_{ym}P_z)₂Cl₂] at room temperature as well as LNT is recorded to authenticate high-spin Fe^{II} state.

Keywords : Iron(II), pyrazole, pyrimidine.

In continuation of our earlier work relating to the interaction of biologically potent pyrimidine, pyrazole and both pyrazolo-pyrimidine based ligands with metal ions, the present note reports coordinating behaviour of the title ligand viz. DP_{ym}P_z with iron(II)¹.

Results and discussion

The analytical data for the complexes along with colours, magnetic moment values and reflectance spectral data are given in Table 1. Conductivity measurements on the complexes could not be carried out due to

Table 1. Characterization of iron(II) complexes

Complexes	Colour	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			B.M (298 K)	Electronic spectral bands Absorption maxima (cm ⁻¹)
		M	N	X		
Fe(DP _{ym} P _z) ₂ Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	Orange yellow	9.87 (9.95)	19.82 (19.73)	12.69 (12.51)	5.10	25640, 20410, 10530
Fe(DP _{ym} P _z) ₂ Br ₂	Reddish yellow	8.75 (8.82)	17.39 (17.48)	25.08 (24.98)	5.35	23810, 10990
Fe(DP _{ym} P _z) ₂ (SCN) ₂	Yellow	9.89 (9.80)	24.34 ^a (24.28)	11.52 (11.10) ^b	5.42	24096, 18180, 11100
Fe(DP _{ym} P _z) ₃ (ClO ₄) ₂	Yellowish grey	6.66 (6.55)	19.61 (19.50)		2.32	25640, 19230
Fe(DP _{ym} P _z) ₃ (BF ₄) ₂	Yellowish grey	6.85 (6.73)	19.55 (19.50)		5.62	18180, 26315
Fe(DP _{ym} P _z) ₃ I ₂ .H ₂ O	Reddish brown	6.22 (6.16)	18.27 (18.34)	27.90 (27.72)	2.49	20408, 10204

^aIncluding nitrogen present in thiocyanate, ^bpercentage of sulphur.

rapid and extensive solvolysis of the complexes. The results of magnetic susceptibility measurements (in terms of effective magnetic moment values) on the polycrystalline varieties of the present Fe^{II} complexes at 298 K reveal that all the present iron(II) complexes except Fe(DP_{ym}P_z)₃(ClO₄)₂ and Fe(DP_{ym}P_z)₃I₂·2H₂O are magnetically normal high-spin complexes ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 5.1\text{--}5.6$ B.M.). The tris chelates of iron(II) have magnetic moment values ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.32\text{--}2.49$ B.M.) intermediate between those normally observed for high-spin ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 5.3$ B.M.) and low-spin ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 0$ B.M.) iron(II) species. The reported iron(II) complexes of 3,5-dimethyl-1-(4',6'-dimethyl-2'-pyridyl)pyrazole having same neutral bidentate (N-N) donor sites as the iron(II) complexes of 3,5-dimethyl-1-(2'-pyridyl)pyrazole² and iron(II) complexes of 2-(2'-pyridyl)imidazole³ are thought to have no significant Fe-Fe interactions in the species. The most reasonable explanation for such magnetic behaviour is, therefore, that there is a thermal equilibrium between high-spin and low-spin states.

The reflectance spectra of the reported spin-free bis-iron(II) complexes viz. [Fe(DP_{ym}P_z)X₂].nH₂O (X = Cl, Br and SCN) are characterized by broad band around 11000 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ⁵T_{2g} → ⁵E_g transition⁴. Absorption band appearing around 18000–20000 and 24000–26000 cm⁻¹ may be of charge transfer origins (*t*_{2g} → π*). The species Fe(DP_{ym}P_z)₃(ClO₄)₂ and Fe(DP_{ym}P_z)₃I₂·2H₂O exhibit in their spectra two very strong CT bands appearing around ~20000 and 26000 cm⁻¹. A comparatively low intensity band around ~1100 cm⁻¹ appears as a broad envelope on the low energy side of the main CT band and in the absence of spectral data at liquid nitrogen temperature it is thought to be a combination of ⁵T_{2g} → ⁵E_g (H.S. type) and ¹A₁ → ³T₁ (L.S. type) transitions in the line with spectral features of Fe(Phen)₂(NCS)₂ at 298 and ~77 K⁵. Electronic spec-

tral data in solution could not be recorded due to appreciable solvolysis occurring on dissolution of the complex species in a solvent.

The IR spectrum of the free ligand furnishes characteristic bands in the region 1600–1400 cm⁻¹ and at 1000 and 750 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned for the νC=C + νC=N and out-of-plane deformation respectively of both 1,2-diazole(pyrazole) and 1,3-diazine(pyrimidine). On complexation, these bands experience positive shift ($\Delta\nu \sim 15\text{--}30$ cm⁻¹) indicating involvement of ring nitrogen in coordination to form five membered chelate ring⁶. In the far-IR spectra of a few compounds, the appearance of bands at 300–315 cm⁻¹ (w) and around 245 cm⁻¹ (ms) attributable to νM–N (pyrazole ring) and νM–N (pyrimidine ring)⁷. The IR spectra of the bis complexes observable at 280 (ms) cm⁻¹ and at 260 (ms) cm⁻¹ (νM–Cl and νM–Br) respectively indicating coordination of halides. N-bonded thiocyanate is inferred from the presence of strong IR bands at *ca.* 2030 and *ca.* 780 cm⁻¹ which are ascribed to νC≡N and νC–S respectively⁸. The lattice nature of water molecules is further substantiated by the appearance of broad diffuse band around 3500 cm⁻¹ in IR spectra. The absence of any recognizable splitting of chloride, bromide and CN of NCS group in the IR spectra of Fe(DP_{ym}P_z)Cl₂ and [Fe(DP_{ym}P_z)₂]Br₂ and Fe(DP_{ym}P_z)₂(SCN)₂ exclude the possibilities of *cis* structure. In the absence of dipole moment measurement and X-rays crystallographic studies above proposition about the geometry of the complexes is highly tentative.

The appearance of broad strong band in tris-perchlorate complex at *ca.* 1110–1070 cm⁻¹ (ν₁) along with other strong one at 625 cm⁻¹ (ν₄) indicate the presence of ionic perchlorate species (Td) in the compound. In fluoro borate complex the broad bands at *ca.* 1120–1040 cm⁻¹ (ν₃) indicate the presence of ionic fluoroborate species in the compound⁹.

The *g*-values [i.e. *g*_x = 2.149 (3), *g*_y = 2.1665 (3), *g*_z = 2.03 (1)] are greater than 2.00 as expected for a more than half filled *d*-shell electronic configuration. The *g*-values are computed from the spectrum using DPPH free radical as '*g*' marker. High-spin Fe^{II} [*3d*⁶, *s* = 2] is an important state in the complex Fe(DP_{ym}P_z)₂Cl₂¹⁰.

Experimental

Preparation of the ligand : The ligand was prepared by condensation of one mole 2-hydrazino-4,6-dimethyl pyrimidine (prepared in our laboratory) with 1 : 1 mole of freshly distilled acetylacetone following the literature method¹¹. The product yielded white flakes on recrystal-

lization from water (m.p. 65 °C). Purity of the ligand was checked by elemental, IR and NMR spectral analyses. All operations were carried out under dry nitrogen as the compounds are air-sensitive. Prior to actual interaction with the ligand, solution of iron(II) salts were treated with trace of iron powder to reduce iron(III) if present any.

Specific preparative methods for the complexes :

$Fe(DP_{ym}P_z)_2Cl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$: A solution of anhydrous ferrous chloride (0.002 mol, 0.25 g) in an aqueous methanol (25 ml) was added to a solution of 3,5-dimethyl-1-(4',6'-dimethyl-2'-pyrimidyl)pyrazole (0.004 mol, 0.8 g) in the same solvent (25 ml). The resulting yellowish red solution was kept under reflux at water bath temperature for 10 min and concentrated under reduced pressure. On cooling the solution in ice, shining microcrystalline compound separated immediately. It was filtered off, washed several times with ice-cold methanol and finally dried under vacuum over fused $CaCl_2$.

$Fe(DP_{ym}P_z)_2Br_2$ and $Fe(DP_{ym}P_z)_2(SCN)_2$: These complexes were obtained by the metathesis of a methanolic solution at $[Fe(DP_{ym}P_z)_2Cl_2]$ with two molar proportion of ammonium salts of corresponding anions at water bath temperature for 30 min. The resulting solution on cooling gradually yielded a microcrystalline product and collected as before.

$Fe(DP_{ym}P_z)_3(ClO_4)_2$ and $Fe(DP_{ym}P_z)_3(BF_4)_2$: The tris-complexes of iron(II) were prepared by interaction of iron(II) perchlorate and iron(II) fluoroborate with the ligand separately in 1 : 3 mole proportions in methanol (50 ml). The compound, thus separated, was filtered off, washed thoroughly with ice cold water and finally collected as before.

$Fe(DP_{ym}P_z)_3I_2 \cdot 2H_2O$: This complex was prepared by metathesis reaction between $Fe(DP_{ym}P_z)_3(ClO_4)_2$ and KI taken in minimum volume of water 1 : 3 mole proportion in methanol (50 ml). The reddish brown solution was obtained. A reddish brown compound separated out, this was filtered off, washed and collected as before.

The iron content of the complexes was analyzed by standard volumetric methods. C, H and N were estimated microanalytically at CDRI, Lucknow. Halogen content was estimated as silver halide by the usual methods. Magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes were measured by a Gouy balance using $Hg[Co(SCN)_4]$ as the calibrant. The diffuse reflectance spectra of the complexes were

taken with a Cary17-D spectrophotometer with a reflectance attachment model no. 1711. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrometer (model no. 577) using CsI phase. EPR spectrum was recorded on Varian E-112 X-band spectrophotometer at room temperature as well as at LNT using DPPH ($g = 2.0037$) as a standard.

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